

EVERSE RSQkit workshop at deRSE25

Background

[EVERSE \(European Virtual Institute for Research Software Excellence\)](#) is a Horizon Europe project that started in February 2024 which aims to create a framework for research software quality.

The EVERSE team is developing the [Research Software Quality Kit \(RSQkit\)](#), a knowledge base to gather and curate resources that will contribute to high-quality software across different disciplines.

We aim to establish the RSQkit as a permanent resource for the research software community well beyond the lifespan of EVERSE.

RSQkit@deRSE25

The RSQkit is a resource which belongs to the research software community and contribution from the community is welcome and needed. EVERSE and deRSE25 are hosting a workshop where the wider community will have the first opportunity to contribute to the RSQkit.

Types of contributions

We are looking for contributions to:

[Task pages](#)

A task page in RSQkit is a structured, community-curated guide that provides practical, actionable guidance for specific research software development tasks. It offers best practices, considerations, solutions, and recommended tools across different software tiers and development stages.

[Tools and resources page](#)

A comprehensive directory of software development tools, resources, and platforms used in research software development.

Science stories

Case stories that provide a comprehensive, narrative-style overview of how software is developed, used, and maintained within a specific scientific domain or research context. We don't have a science story template yet, but some hints at how they should be are [here](#).

Ways to contribute

Minor corrections to existing content

- Example: typos, formatting errors

- With PR from RSQkit website (creates new branch)
- Look for pencil (edit) under the page title

Review of existing content

Example: modification of the content; addition of references; rephrasing; et al.

- Open issue
 - either using the ‘i’ button under the page title
 - or simply create a [new blank issue referencing the page](#)
- And / or
- With PR from RSQkit website (creates new branch)
 - Look for pencil (edit) under the page title

Create new content

- From the [list of topics](#)
 - Either open a sub-issue
 - Or open the [new topic issue template](#)
 - Or work on one of the existing issues
- Pull request a new task page
 - Go to https://github.com/EVERSE-ResearchSoftware/RSQKit/tree/main/pages/your_tasks
 - Open https://github.com/EVERSE-ResearchSoftware/RSQKit/blob/main/pages/your_tasks/TEMPLATE_your_tasks.md
 - Enter edit mode: https://github.com/EVERSE-ResearchSoftware/RSQKit/edit/main/pages/your_tasks/TEMPLATE_your_tasks.md
 - Copy content
 - Create new file: https://github.com/EVERSE-ResearchSoftware/RSQKit/edit/main/pages/your_tasks/my_new_task.md
 - Populate
 - Commit => creates new branch
- If you want to suggest a new topic/task not already listed, follow the above process

Tools and resources

- We are looking for improvements in the wording, resolving inconsistencies, making descriptions more precise, adding tags, alphabetical sorting, removing spaces (blanks) in identifiers and replacing them with hyphens or underscores, etc.
- PR on this file: https://github.com/EVERSE-ResearchSoftware/RSQKit/blob/main/_data/tool_and_resource_list.yml
- This will create a new branch.

Credits and Attribution

Content Ownership

- No single contributor or editor owns the content exclusively
- Content is developed as a community effort with multiple contributors
- Initially, decisions are driven by consensus among RSQkit Editors
- Content can be updated by others without notifying original authors
- Editors ensure content modifications are justified and reflect community consensus

Attribution Structure

- Contributors are formally acknowledged through different roles:
 - RSQkit Editorial Board Members (Editors)
 - Maintainers
 - Internal Contributors (EVERSE project members)
 - External Contributors
 - All contributors collectively known as "Contributors"
- Anyone who contributes to RSQKit is added to the CONTRIBUTORS file
- Different contribution roles include Editors (Editorial Board Members) who moderate the content and act as Maintainers of the repository, and all other general Contributors
- Contributors to task pages will be mentioned in the citation section on the task page they authored

Task Page Citation Guidelines

Task pages are cited using the following format: "[Author Name], '[Page Title]'. everse.software. [http://everse.software/RSQKit/\[page\]](http://everse.software/RSQKit/[page]) (accessed [date])".

This citation is added automatically to the bottom of each task page.

Copyright and Licensing

- Copyright of content remains with authors or their organizations
- All content is licensed under CC BY 4.0 License
- Contributors retain rights while allowing community reuse

Content Management

- Editorial Board reviews and curates content
- Community feedback and updates are welcomed through GitHub issues
- Different viewpoints are accommodated through consensus
- Content reflects popular agreement on topics

This policy balances individual recognition with community ownership, ensuring proper attribution while maintaining the collaborative nature of the resource.

References

https://everse.software/RSQKit/get_involved

https://everse.software/RSQKit/contribution_guidelines#ownership-of-content

https://everse.software/RSQKit/organising_software_project#how-to-cite-this-page